

Implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan in the Private Secondary Schools of Tabuk City

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ABSTRACT

This study evaluated the implementation of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BELCP) in private secondary schools in Tabuk City, Kalinga. Specifically, it determined the respondents' level of awareness of the key elements of the BELCP, the extent of its implementation, and the factors encountered in its implementation. The study used a quantitative descriptive research design. A structured survey questionnaire was administered to 134 teachers from six private secondary schools in Tabuk City. The data were analyzed using frequency, percentage, weighted mean, ranking, and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Findings revealed that respondents were much aware of the key elements of the BELCP, with a total average weighted mean of 2.58. The BELCP was also much implemented among the participating private secondary schools, with a total average weighted mean

of 2.44. However, implementation-related factors were also found to much effect the schools, with a total average weighted mean of 2.48. Significant differences were found in awareness and implementation when respondents were grouped according to sex and school affiliation, while educational attainment did not yield significant differences. For factors affecting implementation, significant differences were observed by school affiliation, but not by sex and educational attainment. The study concludes that the BELCP served as a benchmark for private secondary schools in designing institutional guidelines to sustain educational delivery during the COVID-19 pandemic. It recommends clearer institutional continuity plans, strengthened inclusive education strategies, improved distance-learning support, and continued capacity-building for school personnel.

Keywords: *Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan; private secondary schools; awareness; implementation; distance learning; Tabuk City*

INTRODUCTION

Education remains a major force in individual, family, community, and national development. The Universal Declaration of Human Rights recognizes education as a fundamental right that supports peace, democracy, economic growth, health, and poverty reduction. However, the COVID-19 pandemic disrupted traditional schooling and forced education systems to shift from face-to-face instruction to alternative learning delivery modalities.

In the Philippines, the Department of Education introduced the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan (BELCP) to ensure that learning would continue while protecting the health, safety, and well-being of learners, teachers, and school personnel. The plan included the streamlining of the K to 12 curriculums, the adoption of the Most Essential Learning Competencies, the use of modular and blended learning modalities, the development of learning resources, and the establishment of support systems for schools and learners (DepEd, 2020; Briones, 2020).

The transition to the new normal demanded rapid adjustment from schools, teachers, parents, and learners. Teachers prepared modules, facilitated distance learning, communicated with parents, and monitored learners' progress despite limited resources and uncertainty (Bagod, 2020; Lapada et al., 2020). These conditions were especially important for private secondary schools, which had to align with national policies while adapting implementation procedures to their institutional capacities.

Private secondary schools in Tabuk City faced the same challenge of sustaining instruction during the pandemic. Although the BELCP provided national direction, the actual extent of awareness, implementation, and implementation-related challenges among private schools required empirical evaluation. This study therefore examined how the BELCP was implemented in private secondary schools of Tabuk City and how awareness, implementation, and encountered factors differed according to respondents' sex, school affiliation, and educational attainment.

Literature Review

Education Continuity During the COVID-19 Pandemic

The pandemic created major disruptions in teaching and learning, requiring schools to redesign instructional delivery in ways that reduced physical contact while sustaining access to education. International and local studies described the shift to online, modular, and blended learning as a necessary response to school closures (Basilaia & Kvavadze, 2020; Dayagbil et al., 2021).

In the Philippine context, the BELCP was adopted as the principal policy response for school year 2020-2021. It sought to protect stakeholders from COVID-19 transmission while ensuring that learning opportunities remained available to all learners. The plan was intended not only as an emergency response but also as a framework for continuity, resilience, and institutional adaptation (Briones, 2020; DepEd, 2020).

Key Elements of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan

The key elements of the BELCP included the streamlining of the K to 12 curriculums, the use of alternative learning delivery modalities, the provision of learning resources, the adoption of implementation strategies, adaptation for learners with disabilities, assessment procedures, support for Alternative Learning System learners, and the establishment of committees. These elements guided schools in maintaining instruction while ensuring safety and inclusion.

Capulso (2020) emphasized that the learning continuity plan represented DepEd's commitment to health, safety, and learning continuity during the pandemic. Similarly, Tria (2020) argued that the new normal in education required institutions to invest in teacher training, distance learning systems, and practical strategies for instructional adjustment.

Learning Delivery Modalities and Learning Resources

Learning delivery during the pandemic relied heavily on modular distance learning, online learning, blended learning, home visitation, and other forms of remote support. Modular distance learning became a key modality in many Philippine schools because it was more accessible to learners with limited internet connectivity. However, the effectiveness of such modalities depended on the quality of printed modules, activity sheets, teacher feedback, and parental support.

Toquero (2020) noted that teachers needed professional development to respond to the requirements of online, blended, and distance learning. The present study is aligned with this literature because it assessed whether private schools were aware of and were able to implement the strategies and resources required under the BELCP.

Implementation Challenges

Implementation of learning continuity plans was affected by limited resources, technological readiness, learner adjustment, parental support, and communication systems. Alea et al. (2020) found that teacher readiness, institutional support, and challenges in distance learning shaped the capacity of schools to respond to the pandemic.

In this study, these implementation-related factors were treated as part of the overall evaluation of the BELCP. The focus on private secondary schools is important because these schools were expected to comply with national policy while also mobilizing their own resources and institutional processes.

Figure 1. *Paradigm of the Study*

Paradigm of the Study

Figure 1 presents the original paradigm of the study. It shows the relationship between the implementation of the BELCP and the dependent variables of awareness, implementation, and factors affecting implementation, with sex, school affiliation, and educational attainment serving as moderator variables.

METHODS

Research Design

This study employed a quantitative descriptive research design. The descriptive method was appropriate because the study aimed to determine the status of the implementation of the BELCP in terms of respondents' awareness, extent of implementation, and encountered factors. A questionnaire served as the main data-gathering tool.

Research Locale

The study was conducted in six private secondary schools in Tabuk City, Kalinga: St. Theresita's School of Tabuk, Inc.; Saint William's Academy; Saint Toni's College, Inc.; Kalinga College of Science and Technology; Tabuk Institute; and International School of Asia and the Pacific.

Participants and Sampling Technique

The respondents were 134 private secondary school teachers from the participating schools. The respondent profile included sex, school affiliation, and educational attainment. Female respondents comprised 74.63% of the sample, while male respondents comprised 25.37%. Most respondents were from Saint William's Academy (41.79%). In terms of educational attainment, 91.79% had a bachelor's degree, while 8.21% had a master's degree.

Table 1. *Profile of Respondents*

Profile Variable	Category	Percentage
Sex	Female	74.63%
Sex	Male	25.37%
School affiliation	St. Theresita's School of Tabuk, Inc.	11.94%
School affiliation	Saint William's Academy	41.79%
School affiliation	Saint Toni's College, Inc.	17.91%
School affiliation	International School of Asia and the Pacific	8.96%
School affiliation	Kalinga College of Science and Technology	11.94%
School affiliation	Tabuk Institute	7.46%
Educational attainment	Bachelor's degree	91.79%
Educational attainment	Master's degree	8.21%

Research Instrument

A structured survey questionnaire was used to gather data on the level of awareness of the key elements of the BELCP, the extent of implementation of the BELCP, and the factors encountered in its implementation. The instrument used a three-point Likert scale. For awareness, the descriptions were Much Aware, Moderately Aware, and Aware. For implementation, the descriptions were Much Implemented, Moderately Implemented, and Implemented. For factors encountered, the descriptions were Much Affect, Moderately Affect, and Less Affect.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher secured written permission from the Schools Division Superintendent through the concerned school administrators, including school directors, principals, and learning area coordinators. With the assistance of school heads, questionnaires were administered to the teacher-respondents and were retrieved for tabulation, analysis, and interpretation.

Data Analysis

The data were treated using frequency, percentage, ranking, weighted mean, and one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA). Frequency, percentage, and ranking described the respondents' demographic profile. Weighted mean determined the level of awareness, extent of implementation, and factors encountered. ANOVA tested whether significant differences existed when respondents were grouped according to sex, school affiliation, and educational attainment at the 0.05 level of significance.

Ethical Consideration

The study observed institutional permission before data gathering. Participation was limited to teacher-respondents from the identified schools, and the data were used only for academic purposes. The responses were treated objectively and were presented in aggregate form to avoid identifying individual respondents.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of Awareness on the Key Elements of the BELCP

The respondents were much aware of the key elements of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan, as shown by the total average weighted mean of 2.58. This suggests that private secondary schools in Tabuk City were sufficiently informed about the BELCP and used it as a benchmark in crafting school-level policies and

procedures during the pandemic. The result supports Capulso's (2020) position that the learning continuity plan was disseminated as a major response for ensuring health, safety, and learning continuity.

Among the key elements, strategies obtained one of the highest ratings, indicating that schools were particularly aware of the need for stakeholder partnership, parent orientation, training, open communication between teachers and parents, health protocols, and participation of parents in DepEd programs. This finding is consistent with Tria (2020) and Toquero (2020), who emphasized that teacher preparation and strategic adjustment were necessary in the transition to distance and blended learning.

Extent of Implementation of the BELCP

The BELCP was much implemented in the private secondary schools of Tabuk City, with a total average weighted mean of 2.44. This finding indicates that the schools did not merely recognize the BELCP but also translated it into institutional practices. The implementation covered curriculum streamlining, learning delivery, learning resources, strategies, assessment, and committee formation.

Although the implementation was generally strong, the result also implies that schools had to supplement and complement the national continuity plan with their own procedures. This institutional adaptation reflects the practical reality of pandemic education, where general policy directions had to be localized according to available resources, school capacity, and community conditions.

Factors Affecting the Implementation of the BELCP

The factors encountered in the implementation of the BELCP much affected the participating private secondary schools, as indicated by the total average weighted mean of 2.48. The results suggest that teachers, learners, and schools still experienced challenges despite the implementation of continuity measures. These challenges included adjustment to new learning delivery modalities, resource limitations, communication concerns, and the need for stronger support systems.

The finding is aligned with Alea et al. (2020), who reported that teacher readiness, distance learning experiences, and institutional challenges were central concerns during the pandemic. However, despite these difficulties, the schools continued to implement the BELCP through resourcefulness, institutional cooperation, and coordination among teachers, parents, and administrators.

Table 2. *Summary of Major Results*

Study Component	Total Average Weighted Mean	Interpretation
Awareness on the key elements of the BELCP	2.58	Much Aware
Implementation of the BELCP	2.44	Much Implemented
Factors affecting BELCP implementation	2.48	Much Affect

Significant Differences According to Respondent Profile

The study found significant differences in respondents' level of awareness of the BELCP when grouped according to sex and school affiliation, but no significant difference according to educational attainment. This suggests that awareness may have varied according to the respondent group and school context, while educational attainment did not substantially influence the respondents' familiarity with the BELCP.

For the extent of implementation, significant differences were also found according to sex and school affiliation, while educational attainment was not significant. This indicates that implementation experiences differed across respondent groups and school settings. School affiliation was particularly important because each private school had different institutional resources, leadership practices, and mechanisms for adapting the BELCP.

For factors affecting implementation, significant differences were observed according to school affiliation, while sex and educational attainment showed no significant differences. This reinforces the interpretation that institutional context shaped the degree to which schools experienced challenges in implementing the BELCP.

Table 3. *Summary of ANOVA Decisions*

Area Tested	Sex	School Affiliation	Educational Attainment
Awareness on BELCP key elements	Significant	Significant	Not significant
Extent of BELCP implementation	Significant	Significant	Not significant
Factors affecting BELCP implementation	Not significant	Significant	Not significant

CONCLUSION

The study concludes that private secondary school teachers in Tabuk City were much aware of the key elements of the Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan. This awareness indicates that the BELCP became an important reference for private schools in developing institutional policies and guidelines to sustain educational services during the COVID-19 pandemic.

The BELCP was much implemented in the participating private secondary schools. The schools were able to supplement and complement national guidelines with their own institutional processes, allowing learning delivery to continue despite restrictions, resource demands, and changes in instructional modalities.

The factors encountered in implementing the BELCP much affected the schools. Nevertheless, the continuity of educational services was sustained through the resourcefulness of implementers, the participation of stakeholders, and the ability of schools to adapt the plan to their local context.

The significant differences found according to sex and school affiliation in some areas, and according to school affiliation in the encountered factors, show that implementation was not uniform across respondent groups and institutions. Educational attainment, however, did not significantly influence awareness, implementation, or perceived factors.

Recommendations

1. Policy makers and educational institutions should formulate clear school-based learning continuity plans that include provisions for inclusive education, especially for learners with disabilities.
2. Private secondary schools should strengthen their distance-learning support systems by improving communication mechanisms among teachers, learners, and parents, particularly in modular and blended learning modalities.
3. Schools should explore practical tools such as handheld radios, printed modules, activity sheets, and other locally available communication resources to support monitoring, feedback, and technical assistance for learners studying at home.
4. Continuous teacher training should be institutionalized to improve competencies in modular, online, blended, and alternative learning delivery approaches.
5. School administrators should use the results as a basis for reviewing their institutional implementation of the BELCP, identifying school-specific gaps, and improving readiness for future disruptions.
6. Future researchers may conduct similar studies in other divisions, public schools, or mixed school systems to compare the implementation of learning continuity plans across different institutional contexts.

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